

SHORT NOTES

Isolation of Dictamnine from the Stem-bark of *Zanthoxylum Alatum* Roxb.

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Various parts of *Zanthoxylum alatum* Roxb. (Fam. Rutaceae), viz., fruits, branches, and bark, are reputed to possess distinct medicinal values. The seeds of this plant have been investigated by various workers¹ who have reported isolation of essential oils and hydrocarbons from this source.

The present authors have observed that the stem-bark of *Z. alatum* contains dictamnine [(2,3-b)-4-methoxyfuroquinoline], besides several non-alkaloidal components.

The occurrence of dictamnine has been observed so far in five Rutaceous species, viz., *Dictamnus albus* Linn², *Skimmia repens* Nakai³, *Zanthoxylum ailanthoides* Sieb et Zucc⁴, *Aegle marmelos* Correa,⁵ and *Glycosmis pentaphylla* Retz (D.C.)⁶.

Dried and powdered stem-bark of *Zanthoxylum alatum* (1.3 kg.) was defatted by Soxhletting with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) for 48 hrs. The marc was then extracted with chloroform for 60 hrs. The petroleum ether and the chloroform extracts were separated into an acid-soluble (A) and a neutral (B) fraction. The total aqueous acid solution after careful basification with sodium carbonate was exhaustively extracted with chloroform. The chloroform digest after concentration (8-10 ml) was subjected to chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina, elution being carried out with benzene and chloroform. Chloroform fraction on evaporation furnished an alkaloid which crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless prisms, m. p. 133°. (Found: C, 72.25; H, 4.40; N, 7.13; OMe, 15.62. Calc. for C₁₂H₉O₂N : C, 72.36; H, 4.52; N, 7.03; OMe, 15.57%). IR spectrum of the alkaloid studied in KBr pellet exhibits characteristic absorption peaks at 9.3 μ (furan), 6.2, 6.37 μ (unsaturation and phenyl nucleus), and 13.2 μ (*o*-disubstituted benzene).

The analyses, spectral measurements, and other physical and chemical properties of the alkaloid suggested its identity with dictamnine. It was finally substantiated from its mixed m. p. (undepressed) determination with an authentic sample of the alkaloid isolated in this laboratory by Chatterjee and Roy⁵ and from a comparison of their infrared absorption spectra, which were superimposable.

1. Semmler and Schossberger, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2885; Simonsen and Rau, *Indian Forest Rec.*, 1922, 9, 111.
2. Thoms, *Ber. deut. Pharm. Ges.*, 1923, 33, 68.
3. Asahina *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2045.
4. Tomita and Ishii, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1958, 78, 1441.
5. Chatterjee and Roy, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 267.
6. Chakraborty and Barman, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1961, 24, 121.

The neutral component (B) furnished an essential oil when steam-distilled and the non-volatile portion, when passed through Tswett column containing Brockmann alumina, gave a colorless solid, showing the positive Libermann-Burchard reaction (pink). The characterisation of these neutral components is in progress.

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